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Psycholinguistic Foundations of Natural Language Use in Intelligent Situational Support Systems for Technical System Operators

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**PSYCHOLINGUISTIC FOUNDATIONS
OF NATURAL LANGUAGE USE IN INTELLIGENT
SITUATIONAL SUPPORT SYSTEMS
FOR TECHNICAL SYSTEM OPERATORS**

Abstract. The paper examines the psycholinguistic foundations of using natural language in intelligent systems for situational support of operators of technical systems. The necessity of moving beyond traditional voice alerts and commands is substantiated, and a multifactor model of the effectiveness of speech-based influence is proposed. A multilayer linguistic architecture for constructing voice-based addressed utterances oriented toward optimizing the operator's cognitive state is outlined.

Keywords: *operator activity; situational support; intelligent system; natural language; voice-based addressed utterance; cognitive state; linguistic architecture.*

Introduction. Despite the fact that machine generation of voice messages has numerous practical implementations today, the use of these capabilities in human-machine interfaces remains limited. Systems capable of generating voice messages at operator workstations are primarily intended to ensure operators' situational awareness (perception, comprehension, and projection), which is a narrower task than activity support in the broader sense.

Modern situational awareness systems are capable of generating addressed communicative units realized through spoken natural language in the form of alerts and warnings that have simple content and require literal interpretation. Typically, these are straightforward statements of a fact, event, parameter value, or threat. Alerts and warnings may also be accompanied by prompting a specific action through an addressed command. In aviation, this applies, in particular, to such systems as TICAS, TAWS, Radio Altitude Callouts, and others. The rationale for generating such voice-based addressed messages lies in the need to ensure the immediacy of information perception or execution of effector actions, as well as in reducing the load on the operator's visual channel.

As for modern intelligent aviation systems capable of advising flight crews, performing expert functions, and supporting decision-making, publications devoted to their development do not conceptually consider the voice channel as a means with fundamentally new capabilities. Instead, support is typically reduced to the generation of action alternatives [1].

At the same time, due to its inherent properties, natural language enables not only the communication of facts and the issuing of commands, but also the transmission of messages with high informational capacity and a high level of abstraction, the construction of narratives, discourse management, assistance in resolving dilemmas, and even regulation of the psychological state of operators and entire operator teams. Obviously, these advantages should define the tasks and scope of voice channel use in intelligent systems supporting operator activity, in accordance with specific types of difficulties associated with such activity. This approach is also consistent with the logic of a human-centered approach to the development of artificial intelligence in aviation [2], as well as with the general trend toward reducing the distance between humans and intelligent machines, as evidenced by recent studies [3].

The purpose of this paper is, based on an understanding of the difficulties involved in realizing the capabilities of auditory natural language output in intelligent systems at operator workstations, to propose basic psycholinguistic approaches to

overcoming these difficulties in the interest of increasing the reliability, effectiveness, and safety of complex sociotechnical systems.

Main Part. The actual range of instrumental functions of natural language in operator activity can be outlined through an analysis of a broad set of commonly used types of voice-based addressed utterances employed in speech interaction among members of operator teams that are functionally and hierarchically interconnected. The same functions of natural language may also be realized when an intelligent technical system addresses a human operator, since the regularities of speech-based support are determined by the characteristics of the message and the mechanisms of its perception rather than by the nature of its source.

There are clear functional distinctions between such types of addressed utterances in operator teams as: *Command* (an imperative requirement to perform a specific action), *Warning* (a notice about a potential adverse outcome), *Caution* (a warning against actions that should be avoided due to possible negative consequences), *Corrective Guidance* (guidance on how to correct a situation after an error or misjudgment), *Suggestion* (a possible course of action offered at the discretion of the addressee), *Permission* (an explicit allowance to perform a specific action), *Prohibition* (an imperative requirement not to perform a specific action), *Statement of Fact* (a report of a verified fact), *Situation Description* (a depiction of the current state of the situation), *Narration* (a presentation of the temporal development of the situation), *Reasoning* (an exposition of the reasoning process, including understanding and drawing conclusions), *Assumption* (a statement about something hypothetical-possible but not reliably established), *Question* (a request for information or clarification), and *Praise* (verbal encouragement or positive reinforcement).

This spectrum of addressed communicative units demonstrates that, in their situational reception, there are no strict boundaries between their role in ensuring the operator's situational awareness and their role in regulating activity in a broader sense. An addressed utterance, as a directed communicative unit, takes the form of an utterance in its concrete

speech realization. Each utterance may perform a particular function or combine several functions. For example, while performing an informational function, an utterance may act as a message; however, this informational function may be integrated with prompting, corrective, mobilizing, or other functions.

From this, it can be concluded that an attempt to extend the functional scope of information systems with a voice channel beyond a narrow set of clearly defined situations of operator activity that require the immediate and reliable delivery of a simple message or command would transform any situational awareness system into a system for supporting operator activity with a much broader range of functions. At the same time, situational awareness itself would gain the potential to reach a new level of quality. Conversely, we also believe that as long as the primary meaning of using natural language in intelligent information systems is not defined by the tasks of support in its broad sense, this will continue to constrain the realization of the capabilities of natural language even for the narrower purposes of ensuring situational awareness.

The operator's situational awareness is formed on the basis of a combination of quantitative and qualitative information obtained from both instrumental and non-instrumental sources. Certain types of information are better perceived through conventional instrumental visualizations; however, voice-based messages have exceptional potential for integrating information of different types into a coherent overall picture. Voice messages may rely on generalizations of other speech-based information and may contain interpretations of large volumes of data. Voice-based addressed utterances may also accompany decision-making processes and their implementation. In such cases, their informational function may recede into the background in comparison with their prompting and regulatory functions. The same voice utterance may simultaneously function as a message aimed at informing and as an addressed utterance aimed at influencing the operator.

An operator interprets reality and understands the current situation in its static and dynamic dimensions on the basis of mental representations of various types, which are formed as a

result of integrating perceptual data with the subject's existing knowledge and experience, with the involvement of mechanisms of attention, predictive expectations, goals, motivational and emotional formations that jointly determine the relevance of the overall mental picture. Our theoretical analysis indicates that addressed utterances formulated in natural language have the potential to optimally organize such integration.

The effectiveness R of an addressed utterance realized in the form of an utterance U can be represented as a function of a wide set of variables describing the characteristics of the recipient, which the sender must take into account in order for the utterance to achieve its goal:

$$R_U = f(S, G, M, E, A, K, X, I) \quad (1)$$

where S denotes the situation, and G, M, E, A, K, X, I denote characteristics of the recipient: G – goals, M – motivation, E – emotions, A – attention, K – knowledge, X – experience, I – individual characteristics at both typological and unique levels, which manifest themselves in the psychophysiological cost and quality of perception and processing of the addressed utterance.

It should be noted that the inclusion of parameter I as a separate variable in this multifactor model is based not only on theoretical argumentation but also on preliminary results of our empirical studies [4].

The transition from voice-based situational awareness systems to voice-based situational support systems represents a profound shift in philosophy that requires a rethinking of the functions of machine-generated addressed utterances directed at humans, as well as the development of psycholinguistic foundations for their construction.

The use of the voice channel is evidently constrained by risks associated with individual differences in the perception and interpretation of complex voice-based messages. For situational support systems, these risks may be higher than for situational awareness systems. This is due to the greater complexity of voice-based support tasks, as well as the difficulty of maintaining strict boundaries of standardized vocabulary in situations where the

goal is not merely to inform a person, but to influence their activity, state, focus of attention, and related factors.

From the perspective of activity support, the utterance U functions as an instrument for changing the subject's cognitive state. Accordingly, the cognitive state C_{t+1} , which is formed after the transmission and perception of an utterance, is a function of two variables: the utterance U and the subject's cognitive state prior to its perception C_t :

$$C_{t+1} = g(C_t, U; P) \quad (2)$$

where P denotes a vector of the subject's current characteristics that are relevant for the perception and processing of a particular utterance in a given situation.

It is important to emphasize that this concerns not only the deep meaning embodied in utterance U , but also the combination of its characteristics taken together, such as semantic structuring, syntactic and grammatical organization, the presence of means for managing comprehension, intonation, and others. Accounting for these characteristics requires reliance on a specific model of utterance linguistic architecture that distinguishes a hierarchy of speech layers. The general idea is that the effectiveness of any utterance addressed to an operator of a technical system depends both on its deep cognitive-pragmatic structure and on its surface-level speech realization.

According to our conception of the layers of utterance linguistic architecture, the process of utterance formation requires the sequential passage through the following stages:

- assessment of the necessity to generate an utterance (interactional context layer);
- determination of the target intention (cognitive-pragmatic layer);
- selection of the type of communicative action (discursive-functional layer);
- specification of content (semantic structuring layer);
- selection of the mode of presentation (syntactic-grammatical layer);
- selection of verbal presentation techniques (comprehension management layer);

- realization of voice-based output (modal-realizational layer).

Conclusion. The desired effects of using natural language in intelligent situational support systems for operators of technical systems can be achieved through a wide range of linguistic means; however, they require a coordinated, multi-level approach to their construction based on an integrated model of the linguistic structure of the target utterance.

Utterances with the same target intention may differ in content, linguistic organization, and voice realization depending on situational characteristics and the properties of the subject. Depending on the chosen approach to modifying the subject's cognitive state, such utterances may require literal comprehension or allow interpretative processing, vary in length, differ in style, and convey meaning not only lexically but also through intonational, emotional, and dynamic features of speech.

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